

DYNAMIC RESPONSE OF SANDWICH SHELLS TO UNDERWATER BLASTS

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SUMMARY

This paper presents a general approach for analyzing the response of beam plates and shells to short duration pressure pulses typically encountered as a result of underwater explosions. The problem is formulated in terms of curvilinear coordinates and the resulting equations can then be specialized for each particular geometry. Results are presented for several examples.

Keywords: Composites, Sandwich Structures, Underwater Explosion, Blast Loading

INTRODUCTION

Underwater explosions produce blast waves that can be modelled as exponentially decaying pressure pulses and an oscillating gas bubble. While the effect of the blast wave on composite and sandwich plates has been studied by a number of investigators, the effect of the gas bubble is often ignored assuming that the explosion occurred far away from the structure. With far away explosions, the blast wave can be assumed to have a planar front so that the pressure on the surface of a plate is uniformly distributed. This article describes a general approach for analyzing the response of beams, plates and shells to pressure pulses generated by underwater explosions.

EQUATIONS OF MOTION IN CURVILINEAR COORDINATES

In order to provide a unified framework for the analysis of beams, plates and shells the equations of motion are derived in a curvilinear coordinate system. The coordinates of an arbitrary point are defined by the coordinates α_1 and α_2 along two lines of principal curvatures on the mid-surface and by α_3 in the normal direction. Following Soedel [1,2], for small displacements, the strain-displacement relations are

$$\varepsilon_{11} = \frac{1}{A_1(1 + \alpha_3/R_1)} \left(\frac{\partial U_1}{\partial \alpha_1} + \frac{U_2}{A_2} \frac{\partial A_1}{\partial \alpha_2} + U_3 \frac{A_1}{R_1} \right) \quad (1)$$

$$\begin{aligned}\varepsilon_{22} &= \frac{1}{A_2(1+\alpha_3/R_2)} \left(\frac{\partial U_2}{\partial \alpha_2} + \frac{U_1}{A_1} \frac{\partial A_2}{\partial \alpha_1} + U_3 \frac{A_2}{R_2} \right), \quad \varepsilon_{33} = \frac{\partial U_3}{\partial \alpha_3} \\ \varepsilon_{12} &= \frac{A_1(1+\alpha_3/R_1)}{A_2(1+\alpha_3/R_2)} \frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha_2} \left[\frac{U_1}{A_1(1+\alpha_3/R_1)} \right] + \frac{A_2(1+\alpha_3/R_2)}{A_1(1+\alpha_3/R_1)} \frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha_1} \left[\frac{U_2}{A_2(1+\alpha_3/R_2)} \right] \\ \varepsilon_{13} &= A_1(1+\alpha_3/R_1) \frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha_3} \left[\frac{U_1}{A_1(1+\alpha_3/R_1)} \right] + \frac{1}{A_1(1+\alpha_3/R_1)} \frac{\partial U_3}{\partial \alpha_1} \\ \varepsilon_{23} &= A_2(1+\alpha_3/R_2) \frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha_3} \left[\frac{U_2}{A_2(1+\alpha_3/R_2)} \right] + \frac{1}{A_2(1+\alpha_3/R_2)} \frac{\partial U_3}{\partial \alpha_2}\end{aligned}$$

where the displacements U_1 , U_2 and U_3 are functions of $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3$ and time. For thin shells it is generally assumed that $1+\alpha_3/R_1 \approx 1$ and $1+\alpha_3/R_2 \approx 1$. With the usual kinematics of the first order shear deformation theory

$$\begin{aligned}U_1(\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3) &= u_1(\alpha_1, \alpha_2) + \alpha_3 \beta_1(\alpha_1, \alpha_2) \\ U_2(\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3) &= u_2(\alpha_1, \alpha_2) + \alpha_3 \beta_2(\alpha_1, \alpha_2) \\ U_3(\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3) &= u_3(\alpha_1, \alpha_2)\end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where u_1, u_2 and u_3 are the displacement of a point on the mid-surface. β_1 and β_2 are the rotations of a line segment that initially normal to the mid-surface. With these assumptions the strains become

$$\begin{aligned}\varepsilon_{11} &= \varepsilon_{11}^0 + \alpha_3 \kappa_{11} & \varepsilon_{22} &= \varepsilon_{22}^0 + \alpha_3 \kappa_{22} & \varepsilon_{12} &= \varepsilon_{12}^0 + \alpha_3 \kappa_{12} \\ \varepsilon_{13} &= \beta_1 - \frac{u_1}{R_1} + \frac{1}{A_1} \frac{\partial u_3}{\partial \alpha_1} & \varepsilon_{23} &= \beta_2 - \frac{u_2}{R_2} + \frac{1}{A_2} \frac{\partial u_3}{\partial \alpha_2}\end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

with the midplane strains and the curvatures

$$\begin{aligned}\varepsilon_{11}^0 &= \frac{1}{A_1} \left(\frac{\partial u_1}{\partial \alpha_1} + \frac{u_2}{A_2} \frac{\partial A_1}{\partial \alpha_2} + \frac{A_1}{R_1} u_3 \right) & \varepsilon_{22}^0 &= \frac{1}{A_2} \left(\frac{\partial u_2}{\partial \alpha_2} + \frac{u_1}{A_1} \frac{\partial A_2}{\partial \alpha_1} + u_3 \frac{A_2}{R_2} \right) \\ \varepsilon_{12}^0 &= \frac{A_1}{A_2} \frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha_2} \left(\frac{u_1}{A_1} \right) + \frac{A_2}{A_1} \frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha_1} \left(\frac{u_2}{A_2} \right) & \kappa_{11} &= \frac{1}{A_1} \left(\frac{\partial \beta_1}{\partial \alpha_1} + \frac{\beta_2}{A_2} \frac{\partial A_1}{\partial \alpha_2} \right) \\ \kappa_{22} &= \frac{1}{A_2} \left(\frac{\partial \beta_2}{\partial \alpha_2} + \frac{\beta_1}{A_1} \frac{\partial A_2}{\partial \alpha_1} \right) & \kappa_{12} &= \frac{A_1}{A_2} \frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha_2} \left(\frac{\beta_1}{A_1} \right) + \frac{A_2}{A_1} \frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha_1} \left(\frac{\beta_2}{A_2} \right)\end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

The equations of motion of the shell are derived using Hamilton's principle. For the five independent functions in Eq. 2, the equations of motion are

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{\partial A_2}{\partial \alpha_1} N_2 - \frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha_1} (A_2 N_1) - \frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha_2} (A_1 N_{12}) - N_{12} \frac{\partial A_1}{\partial \alpha_2} - A_1 A_2 \frac{Q_1}{R_1} + A_1 A_2 I_0 \ddot{u}_1 + A_1 A_2 I_1 \ddot{\beta}_1 &= 0 \\ \frac{\partial A_1}{\partial \alpha_2} N_1 - \frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha_2} (A_1 N_2) - \frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha_1} (A_2 N_{12}) - N_{12} \frac{\partial A_2}{\partial \alpha_1} - A_1 A_2 \frac{Q_2}{R_2} + A_1 A_2 I_0 \ddot{u}_2 + A_1 A_2 I_1 \ddot{\beta}_2 &= 0 \\ A_1 A_2 \left(\frac{N_1}{R_1} + \frac{N_2}{R_2} \right) - \frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha_1} (A_2 Q_1) - \frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha_2} (A_1 Q_2) + A_1 A_2 I_0 \ddot{u}_3 &= p\end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial A_2}{\partial \alpha_1} M_2 - \frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha_1} (A_2 M_1) - \frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha_2} (A_1 M_{12}) - M_{12} \frac{\partial A_1}{\partial \alpha_2} + A_1 A_2 Q_1 + A_1 A_2 I_1 \ddot{u}_1 + A_1 A_2 I_2 \ddot{\beta}_1 &= 0 \\ \frac{\partial A_1}{\partial \alpha_2} M_1 - \frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha_1} (A_2 M_{12}) - \frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha_2} (A_1 M_2) - M_{12} \frac{\partial A_2}{\partial \alpha_1} + A_1 A_2 Q_2 + A_1 A_2 I_1 \ddot{u}_2 + A_1 A_2 I_2 \ddot{\beta}_2 &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

in terms of the force and moment resultants which are related to the mid-surface strains, curvatures and transverse shear strains through the usual ABD matrices. In the following, Eqs. 5 are specialized for various beams, plates and shells. While the kinematic assumptions adopted here (Eqs. 2) are commonly used, other assumptions can also be used. Similarly, the linear strains are used here (Eqs.1), when large deflection occur nonlinear terms can be introduced and the same process can be followed to derive the equations of motion.

Straight beams

The equations of motion for a straight beam oriented in the x-direction is obtained using $\alpha_1 = x$, $\alpha_2 = y$, $\partial(\cdot)/\alpha_2 = 0$, $A_1 = A_2 = 1$. Eqs. 5 give the

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(EA \frac{\partial u_x}{\partial x} \right) = I_0 \ddot{u}_x + I_1 \ddot{\beta}_x \quad (6)$$

for axial motion and, for transverse motion, the Timoshenko beam equations

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left\{ GA \left(\beta_1 + \frac{\partial u_3}{\partial x} \right) \right\} = I_0 \ddot{u}_3, \quad \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(EI \frac{\partial \beta_1}{\partial x} \right) - GA \left(\beta_1 + \frac{\partial u_3}{\partial x} \right) = I_1 \ddot{u}_1 + I_2 \ddot{\beta}_1 \quad (7)$$

When shear deformations are neglected, the rotation of the cross-section becomes $\beta_1 = -\frac{\partial u_3}{\partial x}$ and Eqs. (7) can be combined to give the Rayleigh's beam equation

$$-\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} \left(EI \frac{\partial^2 u_3}{\partial x^2} \right) - I_0 \ddot{u}_3 = I_1 \frac{\partial \ddot{u}_1}{\partial x} + I_2 \frac{\partial \ddot{\beta}_1}{\partial x} \quad (8)$$

Neglecting the rotary inertia ($I_2=0$) and the inertia coupling term ($I_1=0$) in Eq. 8 gives the Bernoulli-Euler beam equation.

Curved beams

For the inplane motion of a curved beam, using $R_1 = R$, $\partial(\cdot)/\alpha_2 = 0$, $A_1 = R$, $A_2 = 1$, and, neglecting transverse shear deformation, $\beta_1 = \frac{u_1}{R} - \frac{1}{R} \frac{\partial u_3}{\partial \theta}$. From Eqs. 5 we recover the equations derived by Kang et al. [3].

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{EI}{R^4} \frac{\partial^3}{\partial \theta^3} \left(u_1 - \frac{\partial u_3}{\partial \theta} \right) - \frac{EA}{R^2} \left(\frac{\partial u_1}{\partial \theta} + u_3 \right) &= I_0 \ddot{u}_3 \\ \frac{EA}{R^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \left(\frac{\partial u_1}{\partial \theta} + u_3 \right) + \frac{EI}{R^4} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \theta^2} \left(u_1 - \frac{\partial u_3}{\partial \theta} \right) &= I_0 \ddot{u}_1 \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

Cylindrical shell

For a cylindrical shell, $1/R_1 = 0$, $R_2 = R$, $A_1 = 1$, $A_2 = R$. The motion is governed by

$$\frac{\partial N_x}{\partial x} + \frac{1}{R} \frac{\partial N_{x\theta}}{\partial \theta} = I_0 \ddot{u}_x + I_1 \ddot{\beta}_x, \quad \frac{1}{R} \frac{\partial N_\theta}{\partial \theta} + \frac{\partial N_{x\theta}}{\partial x} + \frac{Q_\theta}{R} = I_0 \ddot{u}_\theta + I_1 \ddot{\beta}_\theta \quad (10)$$

$$-\frac{N_\theta}{R} + \frac{\partial Q_x}{\partial x} + \frac{1}{R} \frac{\partial Q_\theta}{\partial \theta} + p = I_o \ddot{u}_3$$

$$\frac{\partial M_x}{\partial x} + \frac{1}{R} \frac{\partial M_{x\theta}}{\partial \theta} - Q_x = I_1 \ddot{u}_x + I_2 \ddot{\beta}_x \quad \frac{1}{R} \frac{\partial M_\theta}{\partial \theta} + \frac{\partial M_{x\theta}}{\partial x} - Q_\theta = I_1 \ddot{u}_\theta + I_2 \ddot{\beta}_\theta$$

Eqs. 10 are similar to those used by Warburton and Higgs [4] and by Soedel [5] who neglected the inertia coupling terms ($I_1=0$) and the rotary inertia ($I_2=0$). In this form the equations apply whether shear deformations are included or neglected as in [5]. Following Cederbaum and Heller [6], for simply supported boundary cylindrical shells, the boundary conditions are satisfied exactly when the solution is taken as

$$u_x = \sum_{m,n} U_{mn} \cos \alpha x \cos \beta \theta T_{mn}(t) \quad u_\theta = \sum_{m,n} V_{mn} \sin \alpha x \sin \beta \theta T_{mn}(t) \quad (11)$$

$$u_3 = \sum_{m,n} W_{mn} \sin \alpha x \cos \beta \theta T_{mn}(t) \quad \beta_x = \sum_{m,n} X_{mn} \cos \alpha x \cos \beta \theta T_{mn}(t)$$

$$\beta_y = \sum_{m,n} Y_{mn} \sin \alpha x \sin \beta \theta T_{mn}(t)$$

Substitution into the equations of motion (Eqs. 10) gives the natural frequencies and mode shapes and using the modal analysis technique a second order differential equation is obtained for each function $T_{mn}(t)$. In that process, the pressure applied on the external surface of the shell is decomposed in a Fourier series to account for non-uniform spatial distributions.

Spherical shells

For spherical shells, $R_\phi = R_\theta = R$, $A_1 = R$, $A_2 = R \sin \phi$. The equations of motion in curvilinear coordinates reduce to the equations developed by Jahanshahi [7]

UNDERWATER EXPLOSIONS

Following the detonation of an explosive under water, a superheated, highly compressed gas bubble is formed along with a shock wave in the surrounding water and an exponentially decaying shock wave propagates as a spherical pressure wave. Initially it propagates faster than the speed of sound and then it drops to the speed of sound in water. The bubble begins to expand in size and the pressure inside the bubble drops. Because of inertial effects, the bubble over-expands and the hydrostatic pressure becomes larger than the gas pressure inside the bubble. The gas bubble reaches a maximum radius and starts to contract. It will then reach a minimum and expand again. At that time, a second pressure pulse is emitted. The process of expansion and contraction of the gas bubble is repeated several times with the maximum radius of the bubble and the bubble pressure pulse both decaying with time. The gas bubble will also move towards the surface of the water during the oscillation stage.

In terms of the energy released by an underwater explosion, approximately 53% of the energy goes into the shock wave and 47 % into the pulsation of the gas bubble. Damage to the hull of a vessel depends on the stand-off distance of the charge. For large stand-off distances, the effects of the explosion bubble become negligible and many authors focus exclusively on the effects of the shock wave. For large stand-off distances, the shock-wave front is essentially planar while near the explosion the wave –front is spherical. In general the shock wave can cause localized damage on some hull panels but its duration is too small to affect the entire structure of the ship. When the charge is

located near the hull, the effects of the gas bubble collapsing onto the structure and oscillating can be very significant. The pressure pulse is usually described by

$$p(t) = p_0 \exp\{-t/t_d\} \quad (12)$$

where p_0 is the maximum pressure, and t_d is a characteristic of the pulse duration.

TRANSIENT RESPONSE TO A PRESSURE PULSE

Transient response of beams

Previous studies [e.g. 8-11] consider cases for which the characteristic time of the pulse is large compared to the period of the fundamental mode of the structure. Here we will focus on short pulses which have a very different response. With simple supports, the mode shapes of a Timoshenko beam can be written as

$$w = W_i \sin \frac{i\pi x}{L} \quad \text{and} \quad \psi = \Psi_i \cos \frac{i\pi x}{L} \quad (13)$$

after substitution into the equations of motion, the natural frequencies are obtained by solving bi-quadratic equation. Considering the effect of shear deformation alone

$$\left(\omega_i^{SD}\right)^2 = \frac{EI}{\rho A} \left(\frac{i\pi}{L}\right)^4 \left/ \left[\frac{EI}{GA} \left(\frac{i\pi}{L}\right)^2 + 1 \right] \right. \quad (14)$$

When the shear rigidity becomes large, the expression inside the brackets tends to one and the frequencies predicted by Eq. 14 become equal to those given by the Bernoulli-Euler beam theory

$$\left(\omega_i^{BE}\right)^2 = \frac{EI}{\rho A} \left(\frac{i\pi}{L}\right)^4 \quad (15)$$

Table 1: Natural frequencies of sandwich beam obtained using the Bernoulli-Euler beam theory (Eq. 15), including the effect of shear deformation (Eq. 14), using the Timoshenko beam theory and comparison with the results of Marur and Kant [12].

	Present Mode BE	Present SD only	Present Timoshenko	Marur Timoshenko
1	57.94196	57.07353	57.0611	57
2	231.7678	218.741	218.581	216
3	521.4776	461.6527	461.066	452
4	927.0714	759.3299	758.073	736
5	1448.549	1089.848	1087.84	1054
6	2085.911	1438.086	1435.39	1388
7	2839.156	1794.74	1791.5	1749
8	3708.285	2154.503	2150.87	2139

To evaluate the effects of shear deformation and rotary inertia on the behavior of the beam, we consider an example of a simply supported sandwich beam taken from by Marur and Kant [12]. The width of the beam is 1 in., the total thickness of the beam is

0.536 in., the thickness of the core is 0.5 in., the elastic modulus and density of the facesheets are $E_f = 10^7$ psi, $\rho_f = 2.5098 \times 10^{-4}$ lb²/in⁴ and the shear modulus and density of the core are $G_c = 12,000$ psi and $\rho_c = 3.0717 \times 10^{-6}$ lb²/in⁴. The length of the beam is 36 in. The first eight natural frequencies of that beam (Table 1), indicate that the effect of shear deformation is very significant while that of the rotary inertia is small. As suggested by Eq. 14, shear deformation effects become more pronounced for higher modes. While smaller, in this case, the effect of rotary inertia is also more pronounced for higher modes.

For a Bernoulli-Euler beam, the modal expansion approach was used to calculate the transient response of a simply supported beam to a uniformly distributed step pressure load. The transverse displacement and the bending moment are given by

$$w(x,t) = \frac{4pL^4}{\pi^5 EI} \sum_{i=1,3,5,\dots} \frac{1}{i^5} (1 - \cos \omega_i t) \sin \frac{i\pi x}{L} \quad (16)$$

$$M = EI \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2}(x,t) = \frac{4pL^2}{\pi^3} \sum_{i=1,3,5,\dots} \frac{1}{i^3} (1 - \cos \omega_i t) \sin \frac{i\pi x}{L}$$

where $\omega_i = \left(\frac{i\pi}{L}\right)^2 \sqrt{\frac{EI}{\rho A}}$. The displacement response of each mode is inversely proportional to i^5 and the moment response is inversely proportional to i^3 . Therefore, the response is dominated by the first mode and the contribution of higher modes can be neglected. The response to an exponential pulse (Eq. 12) is given by

$$w(x,t) = \frac{4pL^4}{\pi^5 EI} \sum_{i=1,3,5,\dots} \frac{1}{i^5 \left(1 + \frac{1}{\omega_i^2 t_d^2}\right)} \sin \frac{i\pi x}{L} \left\{ e^{-at} + \frac{a}{\omega_i t_d} \sin \omega_i t - \cos \omega_i t \right\} \quad (17)$$

When $\omega_i t_d$ is much larger than one, the response is said to be quasi-static and the contribution of each mode is also inversely proportional to i^5 . When $\omega_i t_d$ is much smaller than one, the response is impulsive and the contribution of each mode is inversely proportional to i in this case.

Transient response of plates

For small deflections, the modal equations can be written in non-dimensional form as

$$\bar{\alpha}'' + \bar{\alpha} = \exp(-\tau/(\omega t_d)) \quad (18)$$

where the non-dimensional time is defined as $\tau = \omega t$. A closed form solution was found and it can be shown that in the phase plane ($\bar{\alpha}'$ versus $\bar{\alpha}$), starting from the origin, the solution quickly settles on a circle of radius $r = \left(1 + \frac{1}{\omega^2 t_d^2}\right)^{-1/2}$. When ωt_d is large $r=1$ and when ωt_d is small, $r \approx \omega t_d$. Note that ωt_d is also the value of the non-dimensional impulse. Figure 1 shows that $r=1$ when $\omega t_d > 10$ and $r \approx \omega t_d$ when $\omega t_d < 0.3$.

Figure 1: Radius of the phase diagram versus ωt_d .

The transient response of plates often leads to large deflections. In that case, following von Karman the two inplane normal strains are given by

$$\varepsilon_{xx} = \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \right)^2 \quad \varepsilon_{yy} = \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial y} \right)^2 \quad \varepsilon_{xy} = \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \frac{\partial w}{\partial y} \quad (19)$$

Approximate solutions for simply supported plates were obtained using a series expansion of the transverse displacements w in terms the linear mode shapes. For a one-term approximation

$$w = a_{11} \sin \frac{\pi x}{a} \sin \frac{\pi y}{b} \quad (20, 21)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \ddot{a}_{11} \rho h + a_{11} \frac{\pi^4}{a^4} (D_{11} + D_{22} r^4 + 2r^2 (D_{12} + 2D_{66})) + a_{11}^2 \frac{4^2 \pi^2}{3a^4} (B_{11} + B_{22} r^4 + r^2 (B_{12} - B_{66})) \\ & + a_{11}^3 \frac{\pi^4}{16a^4} \left(\frac{9}{2} (A_{11} + A_{22} r^4) + r^2 (A_{12} + 2A_{66}) \right) = \frac{16}{\pi^2} p \end{aligned}$$

As in Kazanci and Mecitoglu [13], the Librescu and Noiser [14] example is chosen for comparison. The structure is a three-layer cross ply ($0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ$) square plate ($a = b = 2.54$ m) 0.17 m thick, whose mid-layer is two times thicker than the external ones. The material properties are: $E_1 = 132.4$ GPa, $E_2 = 10.8$ GPa, $G_{12} = 5.6$ GPa, $\rho = 1443$ kg/m³ and $\nu_{12} = 0.24$. The maximum blast pressure is taken to be 3447 kPa. The parameter of the Friedlander's exponential decay function are $\alpha = 2.0$, $t_p = 0.1$ s. Figure 2 shows the linear and nonlinear solutions of the deflection at the center of the plate. Results reveal a good agreement between our linear solution and Librescu and Noiser's results while our nonlinear solution matches well with the Kazanci and Mecitoglu's.

Kazanci and Mecitoglu also analyzed the dynamic behavior of a seven-layer laminate with fiberglass woven fabric reinforcement. The material properties are: $E_1 = 24.14$ GPa, $E_2 = 24.14$ GPa, $G_{12} = 3.79$ GPa, $\nu_{12} = 0.11$ and $\rho = 1800$ kg/m³. The plate dimensions are: $a = b = 0.22$ m, $h = 1.96$ mm. The Friedlander's exponential parameters are: $p_{max} = 28.9$ kPa, $\alpha = 0.35$, $t_p = 0.0018$ s. A one-mode analysis was performed and the results in **Figure 3** are in very good agreement with those obtained in [13].

Figure 2: One-mode approximation.

Figure 3: Nonlinear one-mode approximation

A third comparison was made with the results presented by Akai [15] for simply supported square isotropic plate. The geometry and material parameters are: $a=b=0.25$ m, $h=0.05$ m, $E=21.0$ GPa, $\nu_{12} = 0.25$ and $\rho = 800$ kg/m³. The plate is subjected to a uniform step load of 100 kPa. A single mode and a four-mode analysis were carried out. Figure 4 shows the comparison. Figure 5 reveals a good comparison with Akai's results.

Figure 4: — one mode; ---four modes analysis.

Figure 5: ----Akai; —FEM;plate theory.

Transient response of cylindrical shell panels

The motion of a cylindrical shell of radius R , in terms of the transverse displacement w and the stress function ϕ is governed by two coupled partial differential equations

$$D_{11} \frac{\partial^4 w}{\partial x^4} + 2(D_{12} + 2D_{66}) \frac{1}{R^2} \frac{\partial^4 w}{\partial x^2 \partial \theta^2} + D_{22} \frac{1}{R^4} \frac{\partial^4 w}{\partial \theta^4} + \frac{1}{R} \frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial x^2} + \bar{\rho} \ddot{w} = q \quad (21)$$

$$\frac{A_{12}^2 - A_{11}A_{22}}{R} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} + A_{11} \frac{\partial^4 \phi}{\partial x^4} + \frac{A_{22}}{R^4} \frac{\partial^4 \phi}{\partial \theta^4} + \frac{A_{11}A_{22} - A_{12}^2 - 2A_{12}A_{66}}{A_{66}R^2} \frac{\partial^4 \phi}{\partial x^2 \partial \theta^2} = 0 \quad (22)$$

where the A_{ij} and D_{ij} coefficients are defined in the classical lamination theory for composites and $\bar{\rho}$ is the mass per unit area. No extension-shear or bending-twisting coupling is considered. That is, $A_{16}=A_{26}=D_{16}=D_{26}=0$.

For homogeneous isotropic panels, the non-dimensional frequencies $\bar{\omega}_m$ defined as

$$\bar{\omega}_{mn}^2 = \omega_{mn}^2 / \left\{ \frac{\pi^4 E h^2}{12 \rho (1 - \nu^2) (R \beta)^4} \right\} \quad (23)$$

are written as

$$\bar{\omega}_{mn}^2 = [m^2 + n^2]^2 + \frac{12(1 - \nu^2) L^2}{\pi^4 h^2} \beta^2 \frac{m^4}{[m^2 + n^2]^2} \quad (24)$$

Figure 6: Natural frequencies of simply supported cylindrical panels. (Left: $\beta = \pi/12$, Right: $\beta = \pi/2$).

Considering a cylindrical steel panel with $E= 205$ GPa, $\nu=0.3$, $\rho=7900$ kg/m³ , $h= 1$ mm, $a=b= 0.1$ m, $\beta = \pi/2$ subjected to a unit step pressure pulse, we find that the response contains contributions from many modes (Figure 7).

Figure 7: Modal contributions for cylindrical panel subjected to uniform pressure pulse

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